

ISic1250

I.Sicily inscription 1250

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

accounts

Material

breccia

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del

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1. IG XIV 425, col. I, ll. 1-2; col. III, ll. 27-28; col. IV, ll. 30-31 (V. Arangio-Ruiz):
- 2.
3. [— — — — — — —]αι
4. [— — — — —] σιτωνίω
- 5.
6. . . .
- 7.
8. μία εἴκοσι λίτραι, ἑννέα δέκα ἑξακισχίλια τάλαντα· ἔξοδος τρεῖς [τριά]-
9. κοντα λίτραι, ἕξ ἑβδομήκοντα τριακόσια χίλια δισμύρια τάλαντα·
- 10.
11. . . .
- 12.
13. ἕξ [— — —κό]σια [τάλαντα· λοιπὸν] τεσσα-
14. ρά[κοντ]α [τάλαντα]. ταμίαις ἔσοδος
- 15.

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